

A Fault Tolerant Token-based Algorithm for Group Mutual Exclusion in Distributed Systems

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Abstract—The group mutual exclusion (GME) problem is a variant of the mutual exclusion problem. In the present paper a token-based group mutual exclusion algorithm, capable of handling transient faults, is proposed. The algorithm uses the concept of dynamic request sets. A time out mechanism is used to detect the token loss; also, a distributed scheme is used to regenerate the token. The worst case message complexity of the algorithm is $n+1$. The maximum concurrency and forum switch complexity of the algorithm are n and $\min(n, m)$ respectively, where n is the number of processes and m is the number of groups. The algorithm also satisfies another desirable property called smooth admission. The scheme can also be adapted to handle the extended group mutual exclusion problem.

Keywords—Dynamic request sets, Fault tolerance, Smooth admission, Transient faults.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE mutual exclusion is a classical problem of distributed systems. Jung [1] proposed the group mutual exclusion (GME) problem, a generalization of the mutual exclusion problem, and modeled it as the congenial talking philosophers (CTP) problem. In group mutual exclusion, a process requests a resource type (group) before entering its critical section (CS). Processes requesting the same group are allowed to be in their CS simultaneously. However, processes requesting different groups, must execute their CS in mutually exclusive way. The time interval in which all critical sections executed are of the same type is called a 'session'. An interesting application of GME is, when several users share large data objects stored in some secondary storage (such as CD's), and only one data object can be loaded in the buffer at a time. A solution of group mutual exclusion problem must satisfy the following requirements:

Safety: No two processes, requesting different groups, can be in their critical sections concurrently.

Starvation Freedom: A process attempting to attend a session will eventually succeed.

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Concurrent Occupancy: If some process P , has requested a group X , and no philosopher is currently attending or requesting a different group, then P can attend X , without waiting for any other process to leave the CS. The term 'concurrent occupancy' was first used by Kean and Moir in [2].

Jung solved the GME problem for shared memory systems in [1]. Later on, a number of solutions were proposed using different approaches like, permission-based algorithm [3], token-based algorithms [4-10], and non token-based solutions [11-13]. Out of them, there are only three token-based algorithms for fully connected networks: Mittal-Mohan's TokenGME [8], Mamun-Nazakato algorithm [6] and Swaroop-Singh algorithm [10]. Mittal-Mohan's TokenGME, which is based upon Suzuki-Kasmi algorithm [14], uses two types of tokens, primary token and secondary tokens. The algorithm uses static request sets and its message complexity is $2^{*(n-1)}$. In Mamun-Nazakato algorithm, a session is opened for a predefined time and processes are made aware about it, through broadcast. The processes interested in the currently open session, may join it without incurring any message overhead. However, the algorithm needs that the processes maintain synchronized logical clocks. In [10] Swaroop and Singh presented a token-based algorithm in which each process announces a priority level along with its request. The worst case message complexity of the algorithm is $n+1$. The algorithm favors the request with higher priority levels. This feature makes the algorithm suitable for soft real time distributed systems. The concept of aging is used to remove the possibility of starvation. The algorithm presented in [10] assumes that all channels and processes are reliable.

The token-based algorithms are susceptible to token loss and token has to be regenerated in case token is lost in transit or the site holding the token fails. In the present paper, we propose a token-based algorithm, called DRS_GME henceforth, to solve the group mutual exclusion problem. Our algorithm uses the concept of dynamic request sets. Chang, Singhal, and Liu [15] used the dynamic request sets in their algorithm to solve the classical mutual exclusion problem. The proposed algorithm is capable of handling transient faults [16]. The algorithm also satisfies a desirable property called smooth admission [17], which ensures that when captain is in its critical section, a process requesting for the same group is

allowed to enter in its CS immediately by the captain. The use of dynamic request sets reduces the number of messages per CS request considerably, when the system is lightly loaded. The reason is that the cardinality of request sets will be far less than $n-1$ in that case. In the proposed scheme, a captain process is responsible for the session initiation and sending 'start' message to other processes requesting the same resource type as requested by the captain, in order to allow them to enter in CS as follower. The algorithm uses a distributed scheme, adapted from Manivannan and Singhal [18], for the token regeneration. A timeout mechanism detects message losses due to site failure and (or) communication link failure.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

We assume that the system has n sites, numbered as $1, 2, 3, \dots, n$. The only way of communication between sites, is through message passing. The system is fully logically connected. We assume that, at each site i , there exists exactly one process P_i . Hence, we can use site and process interchangeably. The maximum message delay and the time for which a process can be in its CS are bounded. We also assume that only transient faults occur in the system, and failed sites and (or) communication links will eventually recover. The sites have stable storage (which survives failure), to store local variables.

III. THE DATA STRUCTURES

In our algorithm, the token is a message, which contains an FCFS queue, namely *token.queue*, in order to store all pending requests. The token stores the number of the last completed session in *token.session*. The token contains two more variables (a) *token.type* that stores the type of current session and (b) *token.followers* that stores the number of follower processes. The requests for the same resource are grouped together and treated as one entry in the *token.queue*.

Each process may be in any one of the following six states: *N* (Not requesting), *R* (Requesting), *EC* (Executing in CS as captain), *EF* (Executing in CS as follower), *HS* (Captain but not in CS), and *HI* (Holding token because no request is pending).

The process P_i at site i , has the following local variables:

$state_i$ - the current state of P_i

$captain_i$ - stores the *id* of its captain.

SN_i - is an array of sequence numbers.

RS_i - request set of site i .

old_token_i - a copy of the token is stored in it.

TGI_i - indicates whether the token regeneration process has been initiated by site i .

$follower_i$ - is the set of follower

IV. THE ALGORITHM

The pseudo code of the algorithm is given in Appendix A; however, for reader's convenience a high level description of the algorithm is presented in this section. Our algorithm uses

the dynamic request sets technique and each site stores in its request set the process identifiers, called *id* henceforth, of sites which are possibly holding the token. This request set changes dynamically as the execution progresses. The sequence numbers are used to differentiate between old delayed requests and new requests. There exists a unique valid token and the process, holding this token only, may initiate a session and may work as captain. Initially the process P_i holds the token. A process P_i requesting a resource sends its request to all members in its request set, if it is not holding the 'valid' token. However, if it is holding the valid token in state *HI*, it immediately enters in its CS as captain. If P_i is in state *HS*, it enters in its CS only if the requested resource type is the same as the *token.type* and the *token.queue* is empty; otherwise, the request is added in *token.queue*.

When a process P_i holding the valid token receives a request from P_j for the resource type X , it transfers the token to P_j immediately, if $state_i$ is *HI*. If P_i is in state *N*, *R*, or *EF* it adds P_j in its request set if P_j is not already there. Furthermore, P_i also sends a request message to P_j , if P_j is not in *RS_i* and $state_i$ is *R*. When the request of a process reaches the captain which is executing in its CS, It issues a 'start' message to P_j , if X is the same resource as *token.type*. However, if the request is conflicting, it is added in the *token.queue*. Furthermore, in order to remove the possibility of starvation, if the captain is in state *HS*, it issues a 'start' message only if the request is of the same type and there are no conflicting pending requests.

A process upon receiving a 'start' message enters in its CS as follower and sends a 'complete' message to its captain upon exiting from its CS. When a captain process comes out of its CS, it waits till all its followers have come out of CS and only then it selects next captain from the front of the *token.queue* and passes the token to the next captain if any; otherwise, it holds the token in state *HI*. Whenever a captain process transfers the token to new captain the copy of the token is stored in a local variable *old_token_i*, which is used in token regeneration process. Furthermore, the *id* of processes, which can work as future captain, are added in the request set of current captain before transferring the token to the new captain. As soon as a process P_i receives a valid token (*old_token_i.session* < *token.session*) it empties its request set, delete entry at the front of the *token.queue*, sends an start message to all of its followers, and enters in its CS.

In our algorithm Timer $T1$ is used for detection of loss of a token or request message and timer $T2$ is used for detection of loss of a start or complete message. When timer $T1$ exceeds the value T_{req} the requesting process P_i suspects token loss and it sends the message *gen_token* ($i, SN, X, session$) for token regeneration to all processes including itself and sets a boolean flag TGI_i to indicate that a token regeneration process has been initiated by site i . This flag is reset, when P_i receives a token or 'start' message. When a process P_j holding token receives a request for token regeneration it treats it as a CS request and takes action accordingly. However, if P_j is not holding token and P_j has executed in its CS as captain at least

once after P_i has executed in its CS as captain then P_j generates a new token with the help of old_token_j . P_j selects new captain from $old_token_j.queue$ and sends the newly generated token to it. When a process P_k receives a token, it checks whether the session number of new token is greater than that of older one. If so, it accepts the newly received token as valid token; otherwise, the token is deleted.

When timer T_2 of the captain node expires, it suspects the loss of message 'complete' or 'start' and sends the message $is_complete(j,X)$ to all its follower sites from where it has yet not received the message 'complete'. Upon reception of 'is_complete' message, there could be three possibilities: (a) if P_j is in state EF then P_j ignores it, (b) if P_j is requesting for session X , it enters in its CS, and (c) otherwise, process P_j sends a 'complete' message to the captain.

The value of T_{req} should be chosen carefully so that a token loss is detected well in time and the false token losses go undetected. Let t_m = maximum message delay and t_c = the maximum time period a process will be executing inside its CS. A reasonable value of T_{req} would be $(n+1)*t_m + (n-1)*t_c$. The suggested value for T_{fol} is $2*t_m+t_c$ because in $2*t_m+t_c$ time the captain must have received a complete message from a follower.

Example: In order to provide convenience to the reader, we consider the following example. Let P_1, P_2, P_3 and P_4 be the four processes in the system and let g_1, g_2 and g_3 be the three groups. Initially $token.queue$ is empty, $RS_1 = \Phi$, $RS_2 = \{1,3,4\}$, $RS_3 = \{1,2,4\}$ and $RS_4 = \{1,2,3\}$. We consider following sequence of events:

- (a) P_2 sends request for group g_2 to $\{1,3,4\}$. P_2 's request for g_2 reaches at sites $\{1,3,4\}$, P_1 transfers token to P_2 and P_2 enter in its CS as captain.
- (b) P_1 's request for g_3 reaches at P_2 which is in CS.
- (c) P_3 sends request for g_1 to $\{1,2,4\}$. The request reaches at sites $\{1,2,4\}$, however, P_2 still in CS.
- (d) P_4 sends request for g_3 to $\{1,2,3\}$ The request reaches at sites $\{1,2,4\}$, however, P_2 still in CS.
- (e) P_2 comes out of CS; P_2 adds 1 and 3 in its request set, selects P_1 as new captain, sends token to P_1 . P_1 on receiving token sends start message to P_4 .

Table I describes the changes in $token.queue$ and Request sets with the occurrence of above mentioned events.

TABLE I
 CHANGES IN $TOKEN.QUEUE$ AND REQUEST SETS

event	$token.queue$	Request sets		
After event (a)	empty	$RS_1 = \{2\}$ $RS_2 = \Phi$ $RS_3 = \{1, 2, 4\}$ $RS_4 = \{1, 2, 3\}$		
After event (b)	<table border="1" style="display: inline-table; vertical-align: middle;"><tr><td style="padding: 2px;">g3</td><td style="padding: 2px;">1</td></tr></table>	g3	1	$RS_1 = \{2\}$ $RS_2 = \Phi$ $RS_3 = \{1, 2, 4\}$ $RS_4 = \{1, 2, 3\}$
g3	1			

After event (c)	<table border="1" style="display: inline-table; vertical-align: middle;"><tr><td style="padding: 2px;">g3</td><td style="padding: 2px;">1</td></tr><tr><td style="padding: 2px;">g1</td><td style="padding: 2px;">3</td></tr></table>	g3	1	g1	3	$RS_1 = \{2,3\}$ $RS_2 = \Phi$ $RS_3 = \{1, 2, 4\}$ $RS_4 = \{1, 2, 3\}$
g3	1					
g1	3					
After event (d)	<table border="1" style="display: inline-table; vertical-align: middle;"><tr><td style="padding: 2px;">g3</td><td style="padding: 2px;">1→4</td></tr><tr><td style="padding: 2px;">g1</td><td style="padding: 2px;">3</td></tr></table>	g3	1→4	g1	3	$RS_1 = \{2,3,4\}$ $RS_2 = \Phi$ $RS_3 = \{1, 2, 4\}$ $RS_4 = \{1, 2, 3\}$
g3	1→4					
g1	3					
After event (e)	<table border="1" style="display: inline-table; vertical-align: middle;"><tr><td style="padding: 2px;">g1</td><td style="padding: 2px;">3</td></tr></table>	g1	3	$RS_1 = \Phi$ $RS_2 = \{1,3\}$ $RS_3 = \{1,2,4\}$ $RS_4 = \{1,2,3\}$		
g1	3					

V. PROOF OF CORRECTNESS

In this section, we prove that DRS_GME satisfies the requirements of GME problem namely safety, Starvation freedom, and concurrent occupancy. Let, $type(i)$ = type of resource being used by P_i and $session(i)$ =latest session number executed or being executed by P_i .

Following invariants hold in the system:

$$session(captain_i) = session(i) \quad (1)$$

$$type(captain_i) = type(i) \quad (2)$$

We take the help of the following boolean functions to prove the properties of our algorithm.

$in_CS(i) = true$, if P_i is in state EC or EF , false, otherwise.

$holds_valid_token(i) = true$, if P_i is in state EC, HS , or HI , false, otherwise.

$captain(i) = true$, if P_i is in state EC or HS , false, otherwise.

Lemma 1. There exists at most one valid token in the system.

Proof. We assume, initially P_1 has the token, hence, $holds_valid_token(1) = true$ and $holds_valid_token(i) = false$ for sites $i \neq 1$. This token is transferred from one captain to another captain as the algorithm progresses. In response to $gen_token(i,X,SN,session)$, a process P_j generates a token, only if the condition $(session < old_token_i.session)$ is satisfied. P_j transfers this newly generated token to the site to which it has sent the token most recently. A token received by a process P_i is valid only if $old_token_i.session < token.session$. All the invalid tokens are deleted immediately. The condition $old_token_i.session < token.session$ can be true for at most one token, which is generated by the site that executed in its CS as a captain most recently. Only one such site may exist in the system. Therefore, only one valid token will be retained.

Safety: If two processes are executing in their CS simultaneously then both the CS is of the same type.

Proof: Let us assume the contrary. The two processes P_i and P_j are in CS having their type as t_i and t_j ($t_i \neq t_j$) respectively. Since P_i and P_j are in CS, $state_i = EC$ or EF and similarly $state_j = EC$ or EF . Now, four cases are possible:

Case 1: $state_i = state_j = EC$: This implies that both $captain(i)$ and $captain(j)$ are true. From lemma 1 we conclude that this is not feasible.

Case 2: $state_i = state_j = EF$: From lemma 1 we know that there exists only one captain. Therefore,

$$captain_i = captain_j$$

On applying type function, we get

$$type(captain_i) = type(captain_j)$$

Now, from invariant (2) we can write $type(i) = type(j)$

This contradicts the assumption.

Case 3: $state_i = EC$ and $state_j = EF$

From $state_i = EC$, we observe that $captain(i)$ true.

Now, from lemma 1, only one captain exists in the system. Therefore,

$$captain_j = i$$

On applying type function, we get

$$type(captain_j) = type(i)$$

Now, from (2) we get

$$type(j) = type(i), \text{ which contradicts the assumption.}$$

Case 4: $state_i = EF$ and $state_j = EC$: The proof is similar to case 3.

Therefore, it is proved that if two processes are executing in their CS then both the CS are of the same type.

Starvation Freedom: To show that a request will eventually be serviced following three conditions must be satisfied.

A request will eventually reach the site holding the valid token.

A request that reach the token holding site will be issued a 'start' or 'token' message to enter CS as follower or will be added in *token.queue*.

A request that is added in *token.queue* will eventually be served.

Lemma 2: $\forall i, j : i \in RS_j \text{ or } j \in RS_i$

Proof: Initially $RS_1 = \Phi$ and for all $i = 2$ to n , RS_i contains all other sites except itself. Hence, for any two sites i and j , the condition is satisfied. Now, the request set of a site i changes in following conditions:

- (i) Site i receives valid token : RS_i is emptied.
- (ii) Site j 's request or message gen_token reaches site i and site i is not holding token: j is added in RS_i , if j is not in RS_i .
- (iii) Site i transfers token to new captain j : In this case Site i adds node j and other possible token holders in RS_i , whose requests are in *token.queue*.

The entries from a request set are deleted only when condition (i) holds. However, at this time the site i will be in the request set of all other sites. Therefore, in all above three cases, the request sets changes in such a manner, that the condition $i \in RS_j \text{ or } j \in RS_i$ remains true for any two nodes i and j .

Lemma 3: A request will reach the valid token holding site, if $\forall i, j : i \in RS_j \text{ or } j \in RS_i$

Proof: Suppose when site i makes a request, the valid token is held at site j . Now, $RS_j = \Phi$ because site j is holding the valid token; therefore, site j should be an element of RS_i . Hence, site i 's request will reach at site j . When node i 's request reach site j , there are two possibilities: (i) j still holds the token and (ii) j has transferred the token to next captain, say k . In case (i)

the request of site i will reach the site holding valid token. In case (ii) if k is in RS_i , site i 's request will reach site k . However, if site i is in RS_k , site k must have sent a request message to site i . Consequently, site i will add site k in RS_i , if site k is not in RS_i . Furthermore, site i will send a request message to k . Subsequently, site i 's request will reach the valid token holding site k .

From lemma 2 and lemma 3 the first part of the starvation freedom is proved.

Now, we prove the second part of the starvation freedom. When a request (j, SN, X) reaches the token holding site i , which may be in any one of the three states *HI*, *EC* or *HS*.

Case 1: P_i is in state *HI*: when P_i receives request from site j it will send a token message to j .

Case 2: P_i is in state *EC*: P_i will issue a 'start' message to j if $token.type = X$; otherwise, the request is added in *token.queue*.

Case 3: P_i is in state *HS*: If $token.type = X$ and $token.queue = \Phi$, a 'start' message is issued to j by i ; otherwise, the request is added in *token.queue*.

Now, we prove part three of the starvation freedom. In our algorithm *token.queue* is an FCFS queue and when a session terminates the token is transferred to the process at the front of the *token.queue*. Therefore, a request that is added in *token.queue* will eventually be served. Thus, part three of the starvation freedom will always be satisfied.

Hence, the algorithm ensures starvation freedom.

Concurrent Occupancy and Smooth Admission: In our algorithm, when a process starts execution in its CS as a captain, it sends 'start' message to the processes whose requests are stored in *token.queue* and requesting the same resource. When a captain process executing in its CS receives a request of the same type it issues a 'start' message to allow the requesting process to enter in its CS as follower and hence the algorithm satisfies 'smooth admission' property. However, if captain is in state *HS*, it sends a 'start' message in response of a request of the same type only if $token.queue = \Phi$ (no conflicting pending requests). A requesting process immediately enters in its CS as follower upon receiving a start message. Further if the token holding process is in state *HI*, it will transfer the token as soon as it receives a request message. This implies that, the algorithm satisfies concurrent occupancy property.

VI. PERFORMANCE OF THE ALGORITHM

In this section we discuss the performance of our algorithm based upon following parameters: message complexity per CS request, average message size, forum switch complexity, maximum concurrency, synchronization delay. First, we analyze the performance of our algorithm in fault free scenario.

In the worst case $n+1$ messages needs to be exchanged ($n-1$ 'request', one 'start' and one 'complete' message) per CS entry. However in the best case no message needs to be exchanged. Among the messages used in the algorithm, only

the token has the size $O(n)$. Therefore, in the best case (all processes requesting for the same session), the average message size will be $O(1)$, because one token, $n-1$ 'start', $n-1$ 'complete' and some 'request' messages (depending upon the cardinality of the request sets at each site), will be exchanged. However, in the worst case (all processes requesting for a different session); n token messages will be exchanged, besides the 'request' messages. Therefore, in this case the average message size will be $O(n)$.

In our algorithm all n processes could be executing in their CS concurrently, if the system does not has any conflicting request pending. Hence, maximum concurrency of our algorithm is n . The requests for the same session are grouped together and treated as one entry in the *token.queue*. Therefore, at any point of time there can be at most $\min(n, m)$ entries in *token.queue*. Therefore, the forum switch complexity of the algorithm is $\min(n, m)$.

The synchronization delay of a distributed algorithm generally considered when the system is heavily loaded. Under heavy load conditions, there will always be some request pending, in *token.queue*. Hence, immediately, after captain comes out of its CS and no follower is in its CS, the token is passed to the next captain. Therefore, the heavy load synchronization delay is t_m . However, if the last process exited from CS is a follower, it would send a 'complete' message to the captain that, in turn, terminates the session passing the token to next captain. Therefore, the synchronization delay would be $2t_m$.

Performance in case of message loss: If a token regeneration process has been initiated by site i , it sends a 'gen_token' message to all sites including itself. If site j satisfies the condition $session \leq old_token_j.session$, it would generate a token and forward it to the site to which j had sent the token most recently. In the worst case, n such tokens may be generated and $2n$ (n 'gen_token' and n token) extra messages are exchanged for token generation. However, in the best case, only one site may satisfy the above mentioned condition and only $n+1$ (n 'gen_token' and one token) extra messages need to be exchanged.

In case, loss of 'complete' or 'start' message is suspected, the captain sends 'is_complete' message to all members of $follower_i$ after timer $T2$ expires (value of $T2$ exceeds T_{fol}). $follower_i$ stores id of the processes to which 'start' message has already been sent and 'complete' message is yet to be received from them. Therefore, after expiry of timer $T2$, $follower_i$ will contain id of only those processes whose 'complete' message is lost or which could not finish their CS in time. In our scheme, two extra messages are required for each 'complete' message that was lost, and one extra message for the sites, which are not able to send 'complete' message in time.

VII. EXTENSION OF THE ALGORITHM TO SOLVE EXTENDED GME PROBLEM

Manabe and Park [10] suggested a modification of the GME problem and named it the Extended GME problem, in

which a process is allowed to specify more than one resource type, while making a request. The request made by a process is serviced if the process can be allowed to join any one of the requested sessions. The Extended GME problem removes the possibility of unnecessary blocking.

The proposed algorithm can be modified to solve the Extended GME problem. The 'request' message is modified, and a process P_i , specifies a set of resource types SX in its 'request' message instead of specifying only one type. The process sends such 'request' message to all processes whose id is in its request set. When 'request' message reaches at the token possessing process P_j , P_j checks whether the current session X is in SX , and *token.queue* is empty. If so, P_j sends start(j, X) message to P_i . Otherwise, P_j creates multiple entries of P_i in *token.queue*, one for each member of SX . When a process P_i receives token, it deletes all entries of P_i in the *token.queue*. Similarly, when a process P_i sends start(i, X) message to process P_j , P_i deletes all entries related to process P_j from *token.queue*.

VIII. CONCLUSION

The proposed scheme satisfies the strongest fairness requirement, i.e. FCFS, in addition to the properties like safety and concurrent occupancy. The algorithm satisfies another desirable property called smooth admission. The maximum concurrency of the algorithm is n and the forum switch complexity is $\min(n, m)$. Due to its fault tolerant feature, the scheme is of practical significance rather than being only of theoretical interest. More importantly, the scheme can be applied to another, more complex problem, that is, the extended GME problem. The concept of dynamic request sets has appeared earlier in the literature, nevertheless, its application to handle GME and extended GME problem, is the novelty of the present work. Due to the use of dynamic request sets the algorithm performs better than the algorithms using static request sets when the system is lightly loaded. The comparative performance analysis of the proposed algorithm with other existing schemes is being postponed for the full paper.

APPENDIX

A. The Pseudo Code of the Algorithm DRS_GME

Initialization:
For $i = 1$ to n
 $state_i = N$; $captain_i = NULL$
 $RS_i = \{ids \text{ of all processes except } P_i\}$
 $follower_i = \emptyset$; $TGI_i = false$
 $old_token_i.session = 0$;
 $old_token_i.queue = \emptyset$
 $old_token_i.type = NULL$;
 $old_token_i.followers = 0$
 For $j = 1$ to n $SN_i[j] = 0$
 $state_1 = HI$; $RS_1 = \emptyset$
 $token.type = NULL$; $token.queue = \emptyset$
 $token.followers = 0$; $token.session = 0$

Event 1: P_i request for a forum X

++ $SN_i[i]$

Switch($state_i$)

Case HI:

$token.type=X$; $state_i=EC$

++ $token.session$

$token.followers=0$; Enter CS

Case HS:

If ($token.queue = \emptyset$) && ($token.type=X$)

$state_i=EC$;

Enter CS

Else

Add request ($i, SN_i[i], X$) to $token.queue$

Start timer $T1$

Default:

$state_i=R$; Start timer $T1$

Send request ($i, SN_i[i], X$) to all members of RS_i

Event 2: P_i receives request (j, SN, X)

If $SN > SN_i[j]$

/* otherwise old request

$SN_i[j] = SN$

Switch ($state_i$)

Case R:

If ($j \notin RS_i$)

Add j to RS_i

Send request ($i, SN_i[i], Y$) to P_j

Case EC:

If ($token.type=X$)

++ $token.followers$

reset timer $T2$

add j to $follower_i$

Send start (i) to P_j

Else add request (j, SN, X) to $token.queue$

Case HI:

Add j to RS_i

Add request (j, SN, X) to $token.queue$

$old_token_i=token$; $state_i=R$

Send token ($token.queue, token.type,$

$token.followers, token.session$) to P_j

Case HS:

If ($token.type=X$) && ($token.queue=\emptyset$)

++ $token.followers$;

Reset timer $T2$

Add j to $follower_i$

Send start (i) to P_j

Else Add request (j, SN, X) to $token.queue$

Default:

If ($j \notin RS_i$) Add j to RS_i ;

Event 3: P_i receives start (j)

If ($TGI_i=true$) $TGI_i=false$

Close timer $T1$

$captain_i=j$; $state_i=EF$; Enter CS

Event 4: P_i exits from CS:

If $state_i=EF$

Send complete (i) to $captain_i$;

$captain_i=NULL$; $state_i=N$

Else

If ($token.followers=0$) && ($token.queue=\emptyset$)

Close timer $T2$

$state_i=HI$; $token.type=NULL$

$old_token_i=token$

If ($token.followers=0$) && ($token.queue \neq \emptyset$)

Close timer $T2$

$state_i=N$;

$old_token_i=token$

$RS_i = \{id's \text{ of all processes which are in } token.queue \text{ and will work as captain in future}\}$

P_j at the front of $token.queue$ is selected as captain

Send token ($token.queue, token.type,$

$token.followers, token.session$) to P_j

If ($token.followers \neq 0$) $state_i=HS$

Event 5: P_i receives complete(j)

If (j is in $follower_i$)

-- $token.followers$

Remove j from $follower_i$

If $follower_i = \emptyset$ close timer $T2$

If ($token.followers=0$) && ($state_i=HS$)

If ($token.queue=\emptyset$) $state_i=HI$

Else

If (i 's request in $token.queue$) $state_i=R$

Else $state_i=N$;

$RS_i = \{id's \text{ of all processes which are in } token.queue \text{ and will work as captain in future}\}$

P_j at front of $token.queue$ is selected as captain

$old_token_i = token$

Send token ($token.queue, token.type,$

$token.followers, token.session$) to P_j

Event 6: P_i receives token

If ($old_token_i.session < token.session$) /*otherwise invalid

If ($TGI_i=true$) $TGI_i=false$

Close timer $T1$

delete ($token.queue$) /*delete P_i and its followers

$token.type=X$ /* X is the type of deleted entry

$token.followers = \text{number of followers of } P_i$

Add all followers of P_i to $follower_i$

Send start (j) to followers of P_j

$state_i=EC$; enter CS; $RS_i = \emptyset$

Event 7: Timer $T1$ at P_i exceeds the value T_{req}

Reset timer $T1$

$TGI_i=true$

Send $gen_token(i, X, SN_i[i], old_token_i.session)$ to all sites

Event 8: P_i receives $gen_token(j, X, SN, session)$

If ($SN \geq SN_i[j]$)

$SN_i[j] = SN$

If ($state_i=N/R$)

If ($j \notin RS_i$) Add j to RS_i

If $state_i=R$ Send i 's request message to P_j

If ($session \leq old_token_i.session$)

$P_k = \text{process at the front of } old_token_i.queue$

$token = old_token_i$;

Send token ($token.queue, token.type,$

$token.followers, token.session$) to P_k

Else If ($state_i=EC$)

If ($token.type=X$)

Reset timer $T2$

Send start (i) to P_j

If (j not in $follower_i$)

++ $token.followers$;

Add j to $follower_i$

Else Add request (j, SN, X) to $token.queue$
Else If $(state_i = HI)$
 Add j to RS_i
 Add request (j, SN, X) to $old_token_i.queue$
 $old_token_i = token$
 Send $token (token.queue, token.type,$
 $token.followers, token.session)$ to P_j
Else If $(state_i = HS)$
If $(token.type = X) \ \&\& \ (token.queue = \emptyset)$
 Reset timer $T2$;
 Send $start(i)$ to P_j
If $(j \text{ not in } follower_i)$
 Add j to $follower_i$
 $++token.followers$
Else Add request (j, SN, X) to $token.queue$

Event 9: Timer $T2$ exceeds value $2 * t_m + t_c$ at P_i
 Send $is_complete (i, X)$ to all processes in $follower_i$

Event 10: P_i receives $is_complete (j, X)$

If P_i is requesting for session X
If $TGI_i = True \ TGI_i = False$
 Close timer $T1$; $captain_i = j$
 $state_i = EF$; enter CS
If $(state_i \neq EF)$ send complete (i) to P_j

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